

Talent Management: A Paradigm Shift From Conventional HRM

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this review was to understand the realm of talent management as a paradigm shift from conventional methods used by human resource management. Talent management is a systematized strategic method of obtaining the appropriate talent on-board and help them to develop their prime abilities keeping the organization's goals and objectives in mind. Conventional HRM concentrated on the development of only a small number of high performance-oriented employees in a company. But with advancing technology the conventional HR practices have to re-think their strategy in recruiting and retaining talent to boost organizational performance and profits. This review expounds that talent management by the HRM still looks up to "Star" performers as compared to strategic talent. SME's in comparison to the MNC's are reluctant to change their conventional HR practices. To change these mindsets the firms should support their HR strategies and involve them in their long-term strategy.

Keywords: Talent Management, HRM

INTRODUCTION

Talent management is a systematized strategic method of obtaining the appropriate talent on-board and help them to develop their prime abilities keeping the organization's goals and objectives in mind. Conventional HRM concentrated on the development of only a small number of high-performance-oriented employees in a company (Gallardo-Gallardo et al., 2013). But with advancing technology the conventional HR practices have to re-think their strategy in recruiting and retaining talent to boost organizational performance and profits (Lockwood, 2006).

Talent management is challenging because talent is not available according to demand and supply, sometimes it is limited to one geographical area and due to indiscriminate pay - as qualified people have higher demands) and other areas have unemployment and paucity of talent (Tarique and Schuler, 2010).

There are a lot of questions surrounding how the HR operates, especially in SME's, and what qualities does the HR see in the recruits? Does it look for star recruits or individuals with a strategic focus to employ and retain? Therefore this review is going to delve into the concepts explored by the HR recruitment drives and is there a paradigm shift from the conventional HRM techniques.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Talent Management in MNC's

MNC's have to look at the global context while employing staff and will benefit from a culturally diverse team (Gong, 2017). A study by McDonnell et al, (2011) illustrated that sometimes the HR director is not very well versed with their talent pool.

Another issue with traditional talent management is a discrepancy between demand and supply which results in layoffs of even talented recruits due to oversupply during restructuring (Cappelli, 2008). This problem can be overcome with external recruitment and internal development and training of the existing employees so that they can be further developed with wide-ranging proficiencies in the future which can fit a variety of different roles if needed (Cappelli, 2008). HR can only step out of its traditional mode if it is recognized that it can enhance the company's profitability and has a significant impact (Pfeffers, 1994, 1998).

Multinational companies (MNC) versus SME (Small and Medium Enterprises)

A study done by Stokes (2016) has reflected on the issues of talent management in MNC's vs. SME's found that MNC's have better resources, scale, and scope to absorb better talent.

A survey of one hundred and thirty-two countries by the World Bank (2013), estimated that there are 125 million SME's and 89 million were located in emerging markets. We have to understand that an SME is not like a small MNC department, it has very different uncertainties and concerns economically, behaviourally and organization wise. In SME's, talent recruitment favors mostly Finance, Marketing, and Production activities (Harrison, 2002). HR is more informally organized, flexible, ad hoc in nature rather than being planned, organized, and systematic unlike the MNC's (Thorpe et al 2008). Behaviourally SME's are reluctant to change, risk-averse, close-minded, and do not want to embrace new ingenuities like the MNC's. These issues create a barrier in selecting and retaining talented employees (Burns, 2001).

Focus of HRM

A study was done in Australia (Jones et al., 2012), explored HR's functional focus as to be narrow and individualistic in its approach. The earlier McKinsey research studies (Michaels et al 2001) stated that the importance of retaining people who do well individually, in short- "star" individuals. This theory was quite flawed and according to Beechler and Woodward (2009) as such an individual's performance deteriorates over time. Literature dictates that a strategic attitude of talent management that involves organizational goals like networking, teams, social processes, and not just human resource targets will work better for the organization as a whole (Cappelli, 2009; Iles 2008). The focus must shift from the microfocus of individual talent to the macro focus on team-level issues (Collings and Mellahi, 2009). A qualitative study done by Jones et al, (2012) on senior managers and HR practitioners found that they preferred attracting, retaining, high potential star performers.

Strategic Talent Management

Some organizations identify the future needs of the business in terms of capabilities and skills and recruit them when necessary (Stahl et al., 2007). On the other hand, others use a "talent pool strategy", where they recruit talented people and then find positions for them, but this works out less as such people get disillusioned faster if they land with positions less than their scope of application of skills.

Furthermore the "talent pool strategy" is recognizing pools of people with a potential to move ahead in the future to higher strategic roles (Karaevli and Hall, 2003) and those who can be cast into different groups for different roles if the company changes strategies in the future (Farndale et al., 2010).

Summary

- Along with focusing on productivity, HR must focus on inculcating a culture of teamwork and collaboration for knowledge sharing.
- The knowledge can be used to structure change and flexibility along with investing in training and development.
- A strategic approach must be taken towards the knowledge workers as good performance is linked to implicit knowledge and try and retain such employees who can unceasingly reap from their knowledge and expertise (Kiessling and Harvey, 2006)
- To remain relevant the HRM should align their goals, competencies, and policies to the ongoing strategic management trends.

CONCLUSION

This review expounds that talent management by the HRM still looks up to "Star" performers as compared to strategic talent. SME's in comparison to the MNC's are reluctant to change their conventional HR practices. To change these mindsets the firms should support their HR strategies and involve them in their long-term strategy.

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